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Report on the activities of the PAU Commission on the History of Science in 2020/2021

Abstract

The report discusses the activities of the Commission on the History of Science of the Polish Academy of Arts and Sciences in 2020/2021. It presents the lists of: scientific meetings, conferences, symposia, seminars, new members and new publications.

Keywords: *Commission on the History of Science, Polish Academy of Arts and Sciences, 2020/2021*

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Sprawozdanie Komisji Historii Nauki PAU w roku 2020/2021

Abstrakt

Omówiona została działalność Komisji Historii Nauki PAU w roku 2020/2021. Przedstawiono spisy: posiedzeń naukowych, konferencji, sesji i seminariów naukowych, nowych członków Komisji oraz nowych publikacji.

Słowa kluczowe: *Komisja Historii Nauki PAU, Polska Akademia Umiejętności, 2020/2021*

1. Meetings of the Commission

In the period from October 2020 to June 2021 fourteen scientific meetings of the Commission were held, during which fifteen papers were delivered. Due to the Covid-19 epidemic, all these meetings were online, using the Zoom platform. They were recorded and posted on YouTube and the presentations were posted in the Zenodo digital library:

- prof. dr hab. Andrzej Białas (*PAU* *za Akademicka*), “Steep stairs, or a physicist in the People’s Republic of Poland” (delivered in Polish; 28 October 2020). Dostęp online: [YouTube](#).
- prof. dr hab. Michał Kokowski (L. & A. Birkenmajer Institute for the History of Science, Polish Academy of Sciences), “*Studia Historiae Scientiarum* (ongoing matters)” (delivered in Polish, 28 October 2020). DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.4444939](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4444939)
- dr Mikołaj Getka-Kenig (L. & A. Birkenmajer Institute for the History of Science, Polish Academy of Sciences), “Stanisław Kostka Potocki’s policy towards the Academy of Kraków in the age of the Duchy of Warsaw” (delivered in Polish, 25 November 2020). Available online: [YouTube](#). DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.4521267](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4521267).
- mgr Mateusz Hübner (L. & A. Birkenmajer Institute for the History of Science, Polish Academy of Sciences), “The role of the Polish Academy of Arts and Sciences in building the prestige of the Second Republic of Poland” (delivered in Polish, 16 December 2020). Available online: [YouTube](#). DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.4429657](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4429657).

- dr hab. Marek Rembierz (University of Silesia in Katowice, Faculty of Arts and Educational Sciences, Cieszyn), “Science – history of science – teaching. About the role of the history of science in scientific creativity and teaching by shaping cognitive independence” (delivered in Polish, 27 January 2021).
- dr hab. Stanisław Domoradzki (College of Humanities, Institute of History, University of Rzeszów); Margaret Stawiska-Friedland (American Mathematical Society); Mykhaylo Zarichnyy (College of Natural Sciences, Institute of Mathematics, University of Rzeszów; University of Lviv, Ukraine), “On the importance of the Scottish Book. On the 85th anniversary of its foundation” (delivered in Polish, 17 February 2021). Available online: [YouTube](#). DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.4588878](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4588878).
- dr hab. Piotr Krzywiec (Institute of Geological Sciences, Polish Academy of Sciences), “The 18th-century almanacs, or about slightly forgotten beginnings of geology in Poland” (delivered in Polish, 24 February 2021). Available online: [YouTube](#). DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.4756386](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4756386).
- prof. RNDr. Martina Bečvářová, PhD (Department of Applied Mathematics, Faculty of Transport, Czech Technical University in Prague); Stanisław Domoradzki (College of Humanities, Institute of History, University of Rzeszów), “Mathematics in the interwar period in Central-Eastern Europe. A report on an international research project for the years 2018–2020” (delivered in English (part I) and Polish (part II), 24 March 2021). Available online: [YouTube](#).
- prof. dr hab. Jan Woleński (University of Information Technology and Management in Rzeszów, Poland), “Roman Ingarden’s place in the development of phenomenology” (delivered in Polish, 31 March 2021). Available online: [YouTube](#).
- dr Marcin Krasnodębski (L. & A. Birkenmajer Institute for the History of Science, Polish Academy of Sciences), “Jacques Roger: On Four Styles of Practicing History of Science” (delivered in Polish, 7 April 2021). Available online: [YouTube](#). DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.4757196](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4757196).
- dr Danuta Ciesielska (L. & A. Birkenmajer Institute for the History of Science, Polish Academy of Sciences), “Polish students of Felix Klein” (delivered in Polish, 28 April 2021).

- prof. dr hab. Zenon Roskal (The John Paul II Catholic University of Lublin), “Asteroids in the light of contemporary philosophical concepts. Studies in historical epistemology” (delivered in Polish, 12 March 2021). Available online: [YouTube](#).
- dr Łukasz Mścislowski (Wrocław University of Science and Technology), “Z badań nad dziejami i spuścizną polskich filozofujących przyrodników w Kijowie w latach 1900–1919” (delivered in Polish, 26 May 2021).
- dr Paweł Brzegowy (Association of Lovers of Lwów and South-eastern Kresy), “The villas of the professors of the University of Lwów and the Lwów Polytechnic as residential buildings and workplaces” (delivered in Polish, 9 June 2021).
- dr hab. Wiesław Wójcik (Chair of Philosophy, Faculty of Humanities, Jan Długosz University in Częstochowa), “Antoni Przeborski (1871–1941) – a mathematician from Kharkiv and Warsaw” (delivered in Polish, 16 June 2021).

Thus, the Commission met twice as often at scientific meetings during the Covid-19 epidemic as before the outbreak.

2. Publications

On 30 September 2020 the following work was published:

- *Studia Historiae Scientiarum* volume 19. Edited by Michał Kokowski. Kraków: Polska Akademia Umiejętności, 2020, pp. 612.

In 2020/2021 work was ongoing on the release of the following publication:

- *Studia Historiae Scientiarum* volume 20. Edited by Michał Kokowski. Kraków: Polska Akademia Umiejętności, 2021, pp. 953.

3. Conferences, sessions and scientific seminars organized by the Commission

In 2020/2021 the commission was a co-organizer of:

- “Scientific session on the occasion of the 50th death anniversary of Prof. Władysław Szafer (5 November 2020)”.

Organizers:

- The History of Botany Section, Polish Botanical Society;

- Wladyslaw Szafer Institute of Botany, Polish Academy of Sciences;
- PAU Commission on the History of Science;
- Committee on History of Science and Technology, Polish Academy of Science.

In 2020/2021 the Commission was a co-organizer of three scientific seminars:

- Seminar of the Unit for Science and Science, Institute for the History of Science, Polish Academy of Sciences on 26 February 2021, 26 March 2021 and 10 May 2021.

Organizer:

- Unit for Science and Science, Institute for the History of Science, Polish Academy of Sciences;

Co-organizers:

- PAU Commission on the History of Science;
- Committee of History of Science and Technology, Polish Academy of Sciences;
- Inicjatywa Obywatelska Instytutów PAN (10 May 2021);
- Committee of Science and Science, Polish Academy of Sciences (10 May 2021).

In addition, work is underway to organize four scientific conferences:

- 46th International Commission on the History of Geological Sciences (INHIGEO) Symposium (Kraków, Poland, 18–24 July 2021).

Organizers:

- International Commission on the History of Geological Sciences (INHIGEO);
- Polish Geological Institute National Research Institute;
- Polish Geological Society;
- PAU Commission on the History of Science.

- Dickstein Forum 2021 (Kraków, Poland, 14–17 September 2021).

Organizers:

- PAU Commission on the History of Science;
- International Academy of the History of Science.

Co-organizers:

- Faculty of Mechanics and Mathematics, Ivan Franko National University of Lviv (Ukraine);
 - Institute of History, University of Rzeszów (Poland);
 - Institute of Mathematics, Faculty of Transport Sciences, Czech Technical University in Prague (Prague, Czech Republic);
 - L. & A. Birkenmajer Institute for the History of Science, Polish Academy of Sciences (Warsaw, Poland)
 - Polish Mathematical Society, Kraków Branch (Poland).
- Towards mysteries of the Cosmos with Johannes Kepler – in the 450th anniversary of his birth on 16th October, 2021 (Queen Jadwiga Astronomical Observatory, Rzepiennik Biskupi, Poland)

Organizers:

- Astronomia Nova Association;
 - Jagiellonian University Astronomical Observatory;
 - PAU Commission on the History of Science;
 - L. & A. Birkenmajer Institute for the History of Science, Polish Academy of Sciences.
- Scientific session on “Profesor Adam Strzalkowski (26.11. 1923 – 25.07.2020). *In memoriam*” (PAU, Grand Aula; 26 November 2021, 10:15–3:00 p.m.).

Organizers:

- PAU Commission on the History of Science;
- Jagiellonian University Astronomical Observatory;
- Institute of Nuclear Physics, Polish Academy of Sciences;
- Institute of Physics, Jagiellonian University.

4. New members of the Commission

With the consent of Professor Szczepan Biliński, the Secretary General of the Polish Academy of Arts and Sciences, on January 7–15, 2021, supplementary remote elections of Commission members were held. Ten members were selected (*in alphabetical order*):

- 1) prof. dr hab. Anna Brożek (Institute of Philosophy, University of Warsaw);
- 2) dr Paweł Brzegowy (Tischner European University);

- 3) dr Friedrich Cain (University of Erfurt, Max Weber Center for Advanced Cultural and Social Studies, Post-doc at the University of Vienna);
- 4) dr hab. Mariusz Chrostek, (Institute of Polish Philology, University of Rzeszów);
- 5) dr Krzysztof Duda (Jesuit University Ignatianum in Kraków);
- 6) dr Mikołaj Getka-Kenig (L. & A. Birkenmajer Institute for the History of Science, Polish Academy of Sciences);
- 7) mgr Mateusz Hübner (L. & A. Birkenmajer Institute for the History of Science, Polish Academy of Sciences, postgraduate student at Nicolaus Copernicus University);
- 8) dr Wioletta A. Miśkiewicz (French National Centre for Scientific Research (CNRS) / Nancy / Archives Henri-Poincaré, Director of the e-LV Archives (Kazimierz Twardowski Digital Archives);
- 9) dr hab. Krzysztof Śleziński, (University of Silesia in Katowice);
- 10) dr hab. Przemysław Żukowski (Jagiellonian University Archives).

The Council of the Polish Academy of Arts and Sciences approved the results of the Commission's by-elections on January 26, 2021.

Bibliografia

Current documents of the Commission on the History of Science, Polish Academy of Arts and Sciences 2020/2021.

Kokowski, Michał (ed.) 2020: *Studia Historiae Scientiarum*, vol. 19. Kraków: Polska Akademia Umiejętności, pp. 612.

Kokowski, Michał (ed.) 2021: *Studia Historiae Scientiarum*, vol. 20. Kraków: Polska Akademia Umiejętności, pp. 953.